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Title: SOP for Calibration and Tune the GC Exploris

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Summary

This section describes the Tune, Calibration, and Diagnostic of GC Exploris

- Always make a note about positive or negative calibration of the MS to the Log Book.
- Always make a note about the sensitivity of the instrument, turn on the calibrant and filament, and write notes about the intensity of the calibrant and scanning time (NL: **1E+008** is the minimal recommended value, and Injection Time: **6 ms** is the maximal recommended value) **see Figure 1.**
- Calibrate within the range according to your method, in this case, **70 – 700 m/z**. Alternatively 50 – 550 m/z but always use the same range for the given method. Use ACG target according to your method, in this case, ACG target 100% which is in full scan 1e6.
- Always check the parameters of the Repeller voltage and Lens voltage (1-3), see typical parameters in **Figure 2.**
- When these values are outside the recommended value, clean the source, replace the filament, or check the column. Siloxanes released from the column can also contaminate the source. If you suspect moisture in the MS, bake the Vacuum Chamber (especially if the instrument has been turned off). If this problem persists, call a service technician.
- If you make any changes in the window, always click **Apply** to apply all changes. Or can change tune preferences to enable Hotlink

Preparing MS for Tune/Evaluation/Calibration

1. In Chromeleon GC Exploris software select Thermo MS Tuning ePanel> click System ON.
2. Click on the Optics window > click > Load source settings from file > choose the file from previous measurement > click Apply (values that remain the same and are fixed as follows also in instrument method are followings: **Electron Lens 15 (V)**; **Electron energy 70 (eV)**; **Emission Current 50 (µA)**).
3. Click on the Ion Source window > click Filament > On and wait for a while (let to "burn" for a few minutes to "clean" the filament) and then Turn **Off**.
4. Turn the calibration gas to **On**, select Ionization Mode as **EI**. Turn the Filament **On** and wait for signal stabilization. In Status > Current Scan > TIC Variation should be ~ 1-2% (maximum 5%).

NOTE: Turn on the calibration gas first and then the filament. In case the air is blown out instead of calibration gas the air contact with the filament is prevented.

NOTE: If the system was in Off mode before, it is necessary to put the instrument into On mode for at least 90 minutes before a mass calibration is performed. The filament and calibration gas do not need to be on during this time.

5. Injection time (IT) is typically less than **5 ms**, and the largest peak (NL) height is generally greater than **1E+008** see **Figure 1**.
6. Check that all calibration masses are visible: **68.995; 99.993; 130.991; 196.983; 218.985; 263.986; 413.977; 501.970; 613.964** see **Figure 1**.

NOTE: When calibrating for the 50 – 550 m/z range, the 613.964 mass will not be visible.

#17292 RT:27:06 NL:2.35E+008 Injection Time:3.840
FTMS + p EI Full ms [50.0000-700.0000]

Figure 1. Spectrum of calibration masses

To Tune GC Exploris

7. In Thermo MS Tuning click on the window Optimization and choose the following parameters:
 - Mass selection: TIC
 - Electron Energy (eV): 70 (this parameter is fixed)
 - Auto Tune: ✓
 - Present Defaults: no
 - Set System to Standby on Completion: no/can be chosen
 - Optimize Repeller (V): ✓
 - Optimize Source Offset (V): ✓
 - Optimize Lens 2 (V): ✓
 - Optimize Lens 1 (V): ✓

Optimize Lens 3 (V): ✓

Optimize Injection Flatapole DC (V): ✓

Optimize Inter Flatapole Lens (V): ✓

Optimize Electron Lens (V): no (this parameter is fixed)

Optimize Emission Current (μA): no (this parameter is fixed)

Leak Check: ✓

Tune Report: ✓

8. Click **Optimize**

Ion Source Tune Settings

Parameter	Set value	Read value
Emission current (μA)	50.0	49.0
Electron lens voltage (V)	15.0	15.0
Filament voltage (V)	-64.3	-64.1
Source offset voltage (V)	5.7	5.8
Repeller voltage (V)	7.6	7.6
Lens 1 voltage (V)	-49.7	-49.6
Lens 2 voltage (V)	-2.0	-1.9
Lens 3 voltage (V)	-29.2	-29.1

Injection Filter, Ion Transfer and Ion Trapping Tune Settings

Parameter	Set value	Read value
Injection Flatapole DC (V)	2.2	2.2
Inter Flatapole Lens (V)	2.5	2.5
C-Trap energy offset (V)	0.0	N/A

Figure 2 Typical values of the source parameters

NOTE: Typical value for Repeller voltage is from 7.6 - 8.5 V, if values are higher consider cleaning the source.

NOTE: Perform Tune before measurement of each batch/every day of measurement. The Tune optimizes parameters to obtain the best signal intensity.

NOTE: Before each Calibration or after each maintenance perform Tune (check the parameters if it is similar to the previous Tune (Repeller voltage, Lens voltage 2, Lens voltage 1, Lens voltage 3) see Figure 2. A significant change in parameters means, for example, contamination of the source (see SOP_GC_Q_Exactive_ion Source Maintenance).

To calibrate mass

NOTE: This type of calibration is performed every day/before measurement. Before calibration, the calibrant and filament must be switched on and TUNE performed as described above.

9. In the Thermo MS Tuning window click Calibration > ✓ Mass Calibration (Positive) > click Start.

NOTE: After calibration & before measurement system is typically Standby. Any time the system is placed on standby or off mode, the calibration gas and filament are automatically turned off.

To perform instrument check/Diagnostics

The instrument check should be performed after each maintenance, switching off the mass spectrometer or when a problem occurs. Furthermore, we typically check the device once every two weeks.

Diagnostic is used to check all parameters on the mass spectrometer.

10. In Chromeleon GC Exploris software choose Thermo MS Tuning > click System ON
11. Turn on the calibration gas and filament as described above
12. Click the title bar of the Themo MS Tuning window
13. Click on the icon Diagnostic (small screwdriver - icon at the bottom left) to display it
14. Choose to check a specific part of the device or check the entire device, for example for a preventive check:
 - Ion Optics Connectivity Check: ✓
 - Ion Optics Maintenance Check: ✓
 - Quadrupole Isolation Check (pos): ✓
 - Orbitrap Transient Decay Check: ✓
15. Click **Start** to start the procedure.

NOTE: If evaluation fails, perform calibration (only for fault parameter).

NOTE: Always perform the check first and consider recalibrating the device if the check fails.